

THE IMPLEMENTATION OF INTERNET TECHNOLOGY IN ENHANCING WRITING SKILL OF B1 LEVEL STUDENTS

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Abstract. The significant change of technology drives teachers to have much better teaching performance. Teachers need to incorporate technology into classrooms. The objective of this research is to describe internet technology in developing writing competence of B1 level students including its strengths and weaknesses. Observation, semi structured interviews as well as documents are employed to gain data. Findings show that teachers used technology to develop students writing competence. The strength of the use of internet technology is students' engagement in learning process. Meanwhile, the error system and automatic grammar correction become the weaknesses of the application. Overall, technology can be a means of students to increase students' motivation and creativity in the teaching-learning process, in particular to develop writing skills of B1 level students.

Keyword: Writing skill, internet technology, B1 level students.

Introduction. Writing is considered as one of the most difficult language skills to acquire because writing requires from students being able to use long structures, numerous grammatical rules and building up accuracy and fluency. Writing is also believed as a linear process, since it involves processes such as drafting and brainstorming during pre-writing, proceeded with during writing and editing and revising in post-writing processes. As students write, they may return to previous processes especially during the editing process. Therefore, teachers play an important role in guiding students to improve their writing skills which will be useful for their prospective career.

In addition, there are four reasons to teach writing. First, teaching writing is reinforcement. It means that some students acquire language in oral way, but most of them get it from seeing the language in written way. Second, teaching writing is a language development. The actual process of writing helps them to learn as they go along. Third, it is considered as a learning style. Some students are fantastically quick at picking up language just by looking and listening. Fourth, writing is a skill. It is the most important reason for teaching writing. It is a basic language skill, just as important as speaking, listening, and reading. Therefore, students need to know how to write letters, how to put written

reports together, how to reply to advertisements, and how to write using electronic media.

Recently research on internet technology used in writing class is grown as many researchers see the opportunity to make use internet technology in the writing class. Using internet for language teaching is beneficial for a reading and writing activity when the students are asked to find high quality relevant information for the project or topic, and rewrite the information. With a computer network, a lively class discussion about a topic can begin in writing. The text of that discussion can be stored and printed, or the electronic version can be used to spark thought as students write individual pieces, which they can then post on the network for class members to read and critique, again in writing, after which the student can revise.

Consequently, this research was conducted to investigate the use of internet technology in teaching writing to B1 level students. Particularly, the study examines writing practices and internet technology commonly used by EFL teachers to teach writing skills to B1 level students.

Literature review. As the topic of the research is devoted to the use of internet technology to improve B1 level students' writing skill, it is necessary to provide definitions of writing as well as internet technology suggested by scholars. They are as follows:

From the point of Nunan, writing is one of productive skill which requires the writer to be able to generate ideas and support them with some supporting sentences with accurate and correct grammar. By using correct grammar, the writer can transfer his/her opinions, facts, and experiences well. However, in producing a coherent, fluent, and extended piece of writing is probably the most difficult thing to do in language. [Nunan:1999, p 271].

According to Harmer, there are four steps in the writing process. They are planning, drafting, editing, and final version. In planning, the writers try and decide what it is they are going to say. A writer emphasizes the content and meaning rather than mechanics and conventions when he is in drafting stage. A writer puts down his ideas and thoughts, composes rough draft based on pre-writing and planning activities and considerations. Then, once the writers have produced a draft they then, usually, read through what they have written to see where it works or where it doesn't. The last, once writers have edited their draft, making the changes they consider to be necessary, they produce them final version. [Harmer: 2004, p 11]

As for the idea of Wissick, through the use of technology, students can develop a deeper understanding of content in addition to becoming more

advanced writers and discourse participants. It is possible the greatest potential of multimedia is that it allows teachers to create environments where students can be researchers and creators of products for reports, becoming experts in certain subjects. [Wissick: 1999,p 502].

Additionally, Martin indicates that technology is central to how our students think and act in the world and that literacy is central to education. By using different modalities to learn we are allowing our teachers to give students the chance to understand pedagogical approaches that better integrate new literacy. Due to how fast technology is developing it is important that professional developments are available to educate teachers so students can continue to increase their motivation and abilities to use technology to improve their writing. [Martin: 2008, p 75].

On the basis of the theories given by scholars, the implementation of internet technology in classes to improve B1 level students' writing skills will be conducted and the results will be analyzed.

Research methods. In conducting the research, research design plays an important role in obtaining the data. It is the way information gained from the subjects. In this matter, the writer used descriptive qualitative study as the research design. This design focuses on understanding and meaning through verbal narratives and observations rather than through numbers. Therefore, the result of the research is in the form of description and interpretation of some phenomena that exist during the research. The subjects of the study were B1 level students that the English ability of the students is intermediate.

The data was collected through non-participant observation. It was an observation in which the writer only observed the process of teaching and learning. To obtain the data related to the use of internet technology in teaching writing, students' writing was taken to investigate their writing ability since the use of internet technology was expected to help students to create a written text.

Analysis and result. Considering the research findings, there were some strengths and weaknesses of internet technology in teaching and learning process. The strengths of internet technology in this research were:

- a. Teaching and learning were more effective.
- b. The students were interested in the lesson especially in writing.
- c. The students' writing ideas were well developed.
- d. The students did the task given by the teacher.
- e. The students' knowledge was improved.

While the weaknesses of internet technology in this research as the research findings were:

- a. The students were not controlled when they used internet.
- b. The students frequently opened another sites for teaching and learning process (facebook).
- c. Students needed a long time to access the materials from the internet.
- d. The time management related to the classroom situation (internet connection).
- e. Teaching and learning process became crowded.

Taking all into account, the benefits of using internet technology in teaching B1 level students outweigh the disadvantages. As a consequent, it can be stated that it is highly important to incorporate technology into the classroom while learning to write.

Conclusion. Taking all into account, it is crystal clear that in teaching writing skill, using the internet technology has a great impact not only on language education but preparing students for today's information society. In this modest research, the findings proved in applying the new approach in both teaching and assessing the writing skill is likely to get some positive results but surely, it is not the only way that teachers should follow or adopt. As a result, we can claim that the use of the internet technology has a great impact on students' writing performances. It is a means we have tried and found worth being applied in our classes since it is really motivating.

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